

Original Article

Manufacturing Feasibility Studies on 3D Printable PLA Filament Extrusion by Twin Screw Method and Their Microscopy Studies

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The increasing demand for composite 3D printing has driven significant interest in the development of advanced composite filaments for prototyping and tooling applications. This study focuses on the fabrication and processability of Polylactic Acid (PLA) composite filaments through twin screw method. A conical twin-screw extruder with four distinct heating zones was employed for melt compounding, followed by water cooling and filament spooling. The extrusion process was carefully optimized to achieve a consistent filament diameter of 1.75 ± 0.05 mm, with the highest extrusion temperature set at 170°. The extruded filaments were 3D printed using a Bambu-Lab X1 Carbon Combo 3D Printer with a nozzle of size 0.4 mm as per standards for mechanical testing. Optical microscopy analysis confirmed the uniform dispersion of PLA particles across filaments. Rheological studies indicated shear thinning behaviour across all samples at shear rates above 50 (1/s), making them suitable for fused deposition modelling (FDM) 3D printing. The 5 wt% PLA/SS 316L showed a 26.4% improvement in the ultimate tensile strength and is suggested for tensile loading applications. The 10 wt% PLA/SS 316L exhibited the maximum impact strength of 17.5 kJ/m².

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Introduction

Material extrusion is a type of additive manufacturing process, used in 3D printers where the material has drawn through a nozzle, heated, and then deposited. This nozzle moves horizontally whereas the build platform moves vertically. By this way, layers are formed. As the heating progresses the previous layer attaches with the current layer [1]. Temperature and the chemical agents control the bond between layers. Fusion Deposition Modelling (FDM) is a commonly used additive manufacturing technology in various engineering fields [2]. Over last several years researchers have been able to produce complicated geometric characteristics rapidly in a variety of situations using additive manufacturing technologies [2,3]. The concept was first introduced by Stratasys and Scott Crump included the development of FDM technology at the company in 1989. Using this method, 2D layers are successively laid off along the vertical axis to create 3D structures. Since Hull's original invention, AM is thought to be a rapidly expanding field that has

seen significant technological advancement [3]. FDM used to produce a wide variety of moulded components derived from the filament. The excellence of moulded parts through this process is quantified by tensile strength, surface roughness, and the flexural strength [4]. FDM process, which uses the layer-by-layer manufacturing approach to create parts made of porous materials such as polymer, concrete, metal or a composite is managed by a rapid prototype computer [5]. Using 3D design software, a digital design is created and generated for FDM and then divided into multiple layers. The printer receives this layer data and uses it to reproduce the design layer by layer until the full model is created. Additionally, the re-melting of the existing layer when the successive layer built enhances the layer growth [6].

Materials and Methods

In the present study, PLA granules (supplier: Rever Industries) with an average size of 4mm and with a density of 1.2 g/cc are used to produce as filament. A counter rotating conical twin screw extruder is used for the filament fabrication. The machine contains two gravimetric feeders at top, namely A and B to be filled with the PLA powders which leads to a main hopper underneath. The

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material from the main hopper is directly guided onto the conical twin screw enveloped in a closed chamber. The rate at which material flows into the hopper can be individually controlled for the two feeders. The other end of the conical twin screw is the filament die assembly from which the required size of the filament is obtained.

The region from the main hopper to the die assembly is realised as four zones of different temperatures. The temperatures of the four zones are set to create successive increments in heating towards the die assembly. A vent hole is provided on the closed chamber of the twin screw for the elimination of trapped gases or bubbles

formed due to intermittent material feeding into the main hopper or insufficient material. The twin screw homogenises the polymer powder by the physical mixing methodology. The rotary motion of the conical twin screw forces the melted mixture or material to extrude as a semi-solid extrudate. The extrudate is quenched in a water medium for sufficient cooling and is fed through a nip roll to transform into a solid filament. The rotation of the nip rollers provides sufficient tension to extrude, and the rpm of the nip rollers should be synchronous with the twin screw rpm to avoid any slack or drag. The complete experimental setup and filament are shown in figure 1.

The fabricated PLA-SS 316L composite filaments of all compositions are utilised for the 3D printing of the test specimens for mechanical testing of tensile and impact. The specimens are 3D printed using a Bambu-Lab X1 Carbon Combo 3D Printer with a nozzle of size 0.4 mm. All the test specimens are printed with the following printing parameters as follows: nozzle temperature - 220C, Build plate temperature - 60C, Infill pattern - rectilinear, Infill density - 100%, Layer thickness - 0.1mm and Print velocity - 50mm/s.

Ultimate tensile strength and Young's modulus of the PLA composites are determined through a uniaxial tensile test conducted on a universal tensile testing machine (UTM make: MTS) with a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min. The test specimens for each composition of PLA-SS 316L are 3D printed according to the ASTM D638 type IV standard. A Charpy impact test has been carried out on a WP 400 impact testing machine (Make: GUNT). The test specimens of all compositions are 3D printed as per EN 10045-1 sub-specimen standard.

Results and Discussions

PLA filament morphological studies

The optical microscopy technique is used to acquire the structure and morphology of the specimens under examination. The current study focuses on acquiring the average number of particles in the PLA filaments at three different locations at random. The specimen is a small cut portion of the fabricated PLA filament of approximately 2 cm in length. The specimen is placed in the specimen stage. The mount is rotated to select a magnifying lens of a particular magnification. The brightness is adjusted for the clear vision of the filament details. The software application coupled with the optical microscope is used to match the magnification lens selected, and the magnification required is chosen and the image can be obtained upon selecting the acquire option. The specimen is adjusted after each acquirement to another location of the specimen to acquire the image therein. The coarse and fine adjustments are used to acquire a clear image. The optical microscopic images of the PLA filaments acquired at 5x magnification are presented in figure 2.

Figure 1: Experimental setup and PLA filament production

Figure 2: Surface morphological investigation of pure PLA filaments by optical microscopy at three different locations (a - c)

Flow sweep rheological studies of PLA filament

The application of the filament in additive manufacturing demands the shear-thinning behaviour of its material. Flow sweep rheology test is conducted on the PLA filament. Flow sweep test was carried out on Modular Compact Rheometer 302e, Make: Anton Paar, shown in figure 3 with 25 mm parallel plate configuration. The filament sample is cut into multiple pieces and placed on the base plate of the rheometer. The rheometer base plate is then heated to the temperature of 170°C. The upper plate is brought nearer to the base plate to avoid heat loss. The squeezed material is removed from the edge of the parallel plate geometry carefully ensuring the trim gap of 1.02 mm from the upper plate. The trim gap is set to the measurement gap (1mm) to carry out the further test with a soaking time of 2 minutes at the test temperature. Experiments are conducted on parallel plate configuration with a gap of 1 mm and at a constant temperature of 170°C (highest extrusion temperature) with variable shear rate of 0.001 to 200 (1/s). The variation of dynamic viscosity (mPa.s) and shear stress (Pa) with respect to shear rate are plotted in figure 3 (a & b). It exhibits typical shear-thinning behaviour, where viscosity decreases with an increasing shear rate. This indicates a non-Newtonian flow, commonly seen in polymers due to molecular alignment under shear.

PLA has the lowest viscosity across all shear rates, due to the filler-matrix interactions. There is an almost linear relationship between

Figure 3: (a) Relation between shear rate and viscosity and (b) shear rate and shear stress

Figure 4: Tensile and Impact 3 printed specimens as per the standards

shear stress and shear rate which suggests that the materials follow the power-law model typically, observed in polymer melts and filled systems. This indicates that higher shear rates might be more favourable for processing these materials.

Studies on 3D printability of the PLA-SS316L filament

3D printed PLA-SS316L filaments which are printed and tested for tensile and impact test as per ASTM D638 and EN 10045-1 are shown in figure 4. The tensile test results provide clear insights into the behavior of PLA/SS 316L composites which are shown in figure 5. Pure PLA shows moderate strength and brittleness. Adding SS 316L improves properties initially, with 2.5 wt% showing better strength and strain due to efficient load transfer. At 5 wt%, tensile strength peaks, indicating optimal dispersion and strong particle-matrix interaction. At 7.5 wt%, strain drops despite high

Figure 5: Engineering stress-strain curve of the PLA/SS 316L composites

Table 2: Impact energy of PLA and PLA composite specimens

Specimens	Impact energy (J)	Impact strength (kJ/m ²)
100% PLA	0.60	15.000
PLA with 2.5% SS316L	0.63	15.75
PLA with 5% SS316L	0.67	16.75
PLA with 7.5% SS316L	0.68	17.00
PLA with 10% SS316L	0.70	17.500

strength, due to increased rigidity and stress concentrators. At 10 wt%, agglomeration weakens bonding, reducing performance. The UTS graph shows a peak at 5 wt%, a slight drop at 7.5 wt%, and a sharp decline at 10 wt%. Overall, 5 wt% provides the best mechanical properties.

The impact test results reveal the fracture resistance of PLA/SS 316L composites in table 1. Pure PLA shows ~15 kJ/m² impact strength, reflecting moderate energy absorption and brittleness. Adding SS 316L increases impact strength progressively, indicating effective reinforcement. At 2.5 wt% and 5 wt%, impact strength rises to ~16 and ~16.5 kJ/m² due to better stress distribution and optimal dispersion. Higher contents (7.5–10 wt%) further improve impact strength, peaking at ~17.5 kJ/m² for 10 wt%. Unlike tensile behavior, impact strength benefits from higher particle loading as metallic inclusions aid energy dissipation. Proper control of agglomeration is needed to sustain this performance. Overall, 10 wt% shows the best impact resistance.

Conclusion

PLA filament for FDM 3D printing was successfully manufactured through conical twin screw method. The PLA filament with diameter of 1.75 ± 0.05 mm was extruded at 170°C temperature. The optical microscopy confirms the particles are uniformly distributed along the surface of the filament without any voids. Flow sweep rheological studies confirm the consistent behaviour of filaments at high shear stress with low viscosity when treated with high shear rates. The 5 wt% PLA/SS 316L showed a 26.4% improvement in the ultimate tensile strength and is suggested for tensile loading applications. The 10 wt% PLA/SS 316L exhibited the maximum impact strength (17.5 kJ/m²).

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